

Data & Predictive Analytics: Privacy and Security Impacts

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Abstract

Keywords:

1. Introduction

The digitalization of our day-to-day activities has resulted in a huge volume of data. This data, commonly known as Big Data, is used by many organizations to extract valuable information either to take marketing decisions, track specific behaviors or detect threat attacks. It is also used by the medical field for various analytics and predictive health care analytics. The processing of such data is made possible by using multiple techniques, called Data Analytics and/or Predictive Analytics, which allow getting enormous benefits by dealing with any massive volume of unstructured, structured and semi-structured content that is fast changing and impossible to process using conventional database techniques.

However, while Big Data represents an immense opportunity for many industries, sectors and decisions makers, it also represents a big risk for many users. This risk arises from the fact that these analytics tools consist of storing, managing and efficiently analyzing varied data gathered from all possible and available sources. The consequence is that people become widely vulnerable to exposure because of combining and exploring specific behavioral data. That is, it is possible to collect more data than it should have which leads to many security and privacy violations.

Therefore, research community has to consider these issues by proposing strong protection techniques that enable getting benefits from big data without risking privacy. In this presentation, we highlight the benefits of Big Data and Predictive Analytics and then we review challenges of security and privacy in big data environments in the private, public and hybrid cloud scenarios focusing on two specific platform frameworks; Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure.

Furthermore, I will present some available protection techniques and propose some possible tracks that enable security and privacy in a malicious big data context environment.

2. Aim

Provide a in depth overview of the benefits of big data analytics, the resultant risks associated with big data itself in the cloud and the best security practices which need to be in place to protect the integrity of the data and analytics process.

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3. Material and methods

Summary review of big data application and analytics usage in north America today and where those environments have been successful or failed leading to security breaches and vulnerabilities.

4. Results

In 2017, a study by the Ponemon Institute; 2017 Cost of Data Breach Study: Global Overview indicated that there was an decrease in the cost per data record but an increase in the amount of breaches which had occurred; and the relationship of fluctuations in data breaches across different companies and countries. The problem will continue to cause a threat to privacy and continue to cause an increase in the incidents of Identity Theft, Customer Churn Rate, Business etc.. The importance of Big Data as it grows to the future must be measured and have a direct relationship to the risk of losing the data and the security of protecting the data.

5. Conclusions

Data and Predictive Analytics in today's society has multiple values to many sectors in the industry; understanding the risk associated to vulnerabilities and the requirements to sustain an agile on demand security ecosystem to protect the data and analytics process in all scenarios.

Keywords

Big data, analytics, security, risk

Author biography

David W. Watson currently is a Cloud Security Assessor with Bank of Montreal and has been a leading evangelist within the industry on security; Mr. Watson has held roles from Sr. Engineer to CIO in his career. He is an IT professional with over a three decades of experience in Security & Social Engineering, Compliance, Infrastructure and Solution Architecture in addition to leading multi-platform and hybrid solutions for leading edge IaaS, PaaS and SaaS technologies, with Amazon Web Services, Microsoft Azure and VMWare.

Mr. Watson has concentrated his career on changing the social concepts of security within organizations by mentoring and providing a bridge between the past security concepts and the future of security engineering while continuing to work with emerging technology in security, infrastructure and virtualization. Mr. Watson has been integral in integration consulting of complex enterprise technology platforms and business process re-engineering to global organizations through strategy assessments, process, application and infrastructure engineering.

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